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HYPROMELLOSE AND CARBOMER INDUCE BIOADHESION OF ACYCLOVIR TABLET TO VAGINAL MUCOSA

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ABSTRACT

The present research indicates fabrication of an “economic” controlled release bioadhesive vaginal tablets containing acyclovir using only two polymers; Carbopol 934P (as bioadhesive agent) and HPMC K15 (as rate retardant) to provide therapeutic effectiveness for 12 hr duration. The tablets were prepared by direct compression method. The tablets and their constituent materials were evaluated in terms of micromeritics, pharmacopoeial test, and manufacturing parameters. The release mechanism(s) were also elucidated based on various kinetic models. The characteristics were found to be following: average weight of tablets (355-364 mg); drug content (98.91-101.32%); thickness of the tablets (3.21–3.25 mm); surface pH of the tablet formulation (4.41-4.65), hardness of the tablets (5-6 Kg/cm²) and the friability of the batches was less than 1%. Formulation F7 expressed the higher swelling index owing to the higher concentration of HPMC K15 and carbapol 934P. The drug transport mechanism(s) followed non-Fickian diffusion which coincides with swelling erosion mechanism. The drug release process was observed to be governed by two processes; diffusion as well as erosion (often represented as anomalous diffusion). The current study indicated that the hydrophilic matrix tablet of acyclovir, formulated employing only hypromellose and carbomer can successfully be employed as twice daily, very economic bioadhesive vaginal controlled release dosage form. The formulation was found to be suitable with respect to bioadhesive and sustained release characteristic.

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INTRODUCTION

Acyclovir is an antiviral agent that is used for treating herpes simplex virus infections (type-I/II). Generally, for years, it has been administered through oral routes or to some extent by cream. The low bioavailability (~20%), high volume of distribution (32-61 L), rapid metabolism by viral thymidine kinase, plasma elimination half-life of 2.5 hr, and rapid urinary excretion have resulted in reduced effectiveness at the site of action [1]. Acyclovir suffers from the problem of solubility under both hydrophilic and lipophilic conditions which lead to high variability in therapy [2]. Therefore, in order to amplify the therapeutic effectiveness by elevating the bioavailability, several rational strategies have been applied for over the years, like the liposomal system [3], intravenous [4], intravaginal ring [5], transbuccal [6], mucoadhesive microsphere [7], suspension [8], mucoadhesive nanoparticles [9], bioadhesive gel [10], nasal Hydrogels [11], floating systems [12], etc.

The bioadhesive materials have the attribute to bind the mucin layer of a biological membrane to achieve systemic delivery of the drug through the different mucosa [13]. Several dosage forms including tablets, patches, tapes, firm, semisolid, and powders are delivered using bioadhesive polymers which are non-ionic or anionic hydrophilicity with numerous hydrogen bond-forming group, suitable surface property for wetting mucus/ mucosal tissue surfaces, and sufficient flexibility to penetrate the mucus network or tissue crevices [14]. The vaginal based bioadhesive systems have been an impressive strategy to design tablet formulations which could elevate the bioavailability and will also offer controlled release for 12 hr period [15]. In an outline, it might be understood that the fabricated formulation will tender patient compliance.

The vagina, as a site for drug delivery, offers certain unique features that can be exploited in order to achieve desirable therapeutic effects for the local and systemic delivery of drugs, specifically for female-related disorders. Traditionally, the vaginal cavity has been used for the delivery of locally acting drugs such as antibacterial, antifungal, antiprotozoal, antiviral, labor-inducing and spermicidal agents, prostaglandins and steroids [16]. This route provides advantages such as reducing or eliminating the incidence and severity of side effects, being a non-invasive route of administration and accessibility [17]. These benefits could contribute to a better compliance, thus achieving an improved therapeutic outcome. Furthermore, the vagina possesses properties which include: large surface area of the vaginal wall, permeability, a rich blood supply and importantly, the ability to bypass first-pass liver metabolism [18]. These properties are considered to be advantageous in relation to drug absorption. Currently, there are a variety of pharmaceutical products available on the market designed for intravaginal therapy (tablets, creams, suppositories, pessaries, foams, solutions, ointments, and gels). Furthermore, the vagina has unique features in terms of microflora, pH, and cyclic changes, and these factors influence the performance of the formulations and must be considered during the development and evaluation of vaginal delivery systems [19]. Therefore, a successful delivery of drugs through the vagina represents a pharmaceutical challenge.

Numerous papers have been reported on acyclovir bioadhesive vaginal tablets which had utilized polyacrylic acid, xanthan gum, methylcellulose, chitosan, carboxymethyl cellulose, carrageenan, hydroxypropyl cellulose, carbopol 934P, and hydroxypropylmethyl cellulose as a bioadhesive [20-22]. The present research indicates fabrication of an "economic" controlled release bioadhesive vaginal tablets containing acyclovir using only two polymers; Carbopol 934P (as bioadhesive agent) and HPMC K15 (as rate retardant) to provide therapeutic effectiveness for 12 hr duration as well as to bypass the rapid metabolism. The prepared tablets and constituent materials were evaluated in terms of micromeritics, pharmacopoeial test, and manufacturing parameters. The release mechanism(s) were also elucidated based on various kinetic models of Zero-order, First-order, Higuchi, Korsmeyer-Peppas, and Hixson-Crowell models.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals

Acyclovir was obtained as a generous gift from Matrix Labs, Sinnar, India. HPMC K15, Carbopol 934P, Talc, Microcrystalline cellulose, Sodium acetate, and Glacial acetic acid were purchased from Molychem Ltd., Mumbai, India. All other reagents used in the study were of analytical grade. Double distilled water was used for the experiment.

Instruments

Spectroscopic analysis was carried out using double-beam Shimadzu® Ultraviolet-Visible Spectrophotometer (Model UV-1800, Kyoto, Japan) connected to a computer having a spectral bandwidth of 1 nm and wavelength accuracy of ± 0.3 nm with a pair of 10 mm path length matched quartz cells was used. All weighing were performed using Shimadzu® electronic balance (Model AUW220D, Kyoto, Japan). FT-IR was performed using Shimadzu® IRAffinity-1S instrument employing KBr disc. Vernier caliper (Indian caliper, Ambala, India), Roche friabilator (Electrolab, India), Dissolution test apparatus (Electrolab, India), Pfizer hardness tester (Pfizer, Spacelabs, India) were employed for evaluation of tablets. Stability chamber (Bio-Technics, India) was employed for accelerated stability studies.

Formulation

The bioadhesive controlled acyclovir matrix tablets were prepared by direct compression method. Acyclovir and various concentration of HPMC K-15M were used as a release retardant polymer, whereas the carbopol 934P was used as bioadhesive polymer. The other excipient used was micro crystalline cellulose for its diluents property. The contents were first sieved and then blended in a mortar with a pestle to obtain uniform mixing. Finally, talc was mixed for the lubrication purpose which was then compressed by Chamunda PP-II multi-station machine using 10 mm flat punch. The weight of tablet was adjusted to 360 mg and each tablet contained 200 mg of acyclovir. Table 1 depicts the chart for tablet formulation.

Table 1. Formulation of acyclovir bioadhesive tablet.

Ingredients (mg)	Formulations								
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Acyclovir	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200
Carbopol 934P	15	10	10	15	20	20	20	10	15
HPMC K15	35	35	25	30	30	25	35	30	25
MCC	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110
Talc	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

HPMC, hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose; MCC, microcrystalline cellulose.

Drug-Interaction Studies

The interaction of acyclovir with the polymers HPMC K15 and Carbopol 934P was determined by Fourier transformed infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy to examine the compatibility in the formulation. In order to verify any type of interaction(s); FT-IR spectra of acyclovir, HPMC K15, Carbopol 934P, and the physical mixture was taken [23].

Micromeritic characterization

The micromeritics characteristic parameters were evaluated in terms of bulk density, tapped density, angle of repose, Hausner's ratio, and Carr's index for the drug and the polymers. The angle of repose was determined by funnel method, bulk and tapped density by cylinder method, and Carr's index (CI) and Hausner's ratio (HR) was calculated according to the formula.

Evaluation of Tablets

Thickness

The thickness and diameter of the fabricated tablets were measured by vernier caliper and the results were expressed as mean values of 10 determinations, with standard deviations.

Hardness

The Monsanto hardness tester was used to determine the tablet hardness. The tablet was held between a fixed and moving jaw, the body of Monsanto hardness tester carries an adjustable scale which was set a zero against an index mark fixed to the compression plunger. When the tablet was held between the jaws, the load was gradually increased until the tablet fractured. The value of the load at the point gave a measure of the tablet hardness.

Friability

The friability of the bioadhesive vaginal tablets was evaluated by friability test apparatus known as Roach's friabilator. Twenty weighed tablet were initially weighed and placed in the friabilator. The system was operated at 25 rpm for 4 minutes. The tablets were then removed and weighed again. The friability of the tablets was determined by the following formula and expressed in percentage. According to the pharmacopoeial guidelines, a value less than 1% indicates that the test is passed.

$$\text{Friability} = 1 - \frac{W_o}{W} \times 100$$

where, f is friability, W_o is the weight of the tablet before the test, and W is the weight of tablet after the test.

Weight variation test

Individually, twenty tablets were weighed and the average weight was calculated. The individual weights of the tablets were subsequently compared with the average weight. The tablet passes the test, if not more than two tablets fall outside the percentage limit and none of the tablets differ by more than double the percentage limit given in Indian Pharmacopoeia.

Drug content uniformity

20 tablets were weighed and crushed uniformly. A quantity of the powder equivalent to 0.1 g of acyclovir was weighed and dissolved in 60 mL of 0.1 M sodium hydroxide with the aid of sonication for 15 minutes. The volume was made up to 100 mL by 0.1 M sodium hydroxide and the content was filtered. 10 mL of the above filtrate was pipette out to another volumetric flask, to it 50 mL of distilled water and 5.8 mL of 2 M hydrochloric acid was added and additionally, the volume was made up to 100.0 mL by distilled water. 5.0 mL of the resulting solution was taken and sufficient amount of 0.1 M hydrochloric acid was added to produce 50.0 mL and the content was mixed well. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 255 nm employing 0.1 M hydrochloric acid as blank.

Swelling index

From each formulation, a single tablet was taken and weighed individually (W_0). Afterward, the tablet was placed separately in a petridish containing 5 mL of acetate buffer of pH 4.6 for 30 minutes at room temperature. The fabricated tablet was then removed from petridish and excess of liquid was removed carefully by filter paper. The swollen bioadhesive tablet was further weighed (W) and the percentage swelling index was calculated. The experiment was conducted in a triplicate manner and the average reading was taken. The swelling index of the tablet was determined by the following formula:

$$\text{Swelling index} = \frac{W - W_0}{W_0} \times 100$$

where, W is the final weight, W_0 is the initial weight

Surface pH Study

The surface pH of the prepared vaginal tablets was determined in order to investigate the possibility *in vivo* local irritation as more acidic or alkaline pH cause discomfort to the vaginal mucosa. A pH of 5.5-6.5 (weakly acidic) is desirable as closely as possible since the pH of vagina falls in that range. For measuring the surface pH, a combined glass electrode was employed. The tablet was initially allowed to swell by keeping it in contact with 1 ml of acetate buffer (pH 4.4 ± 0.05) for 2 hr at room temperature. The pH was measured by bringing the electrode in contact with the surface of the tablet and allowing it to equilibrate for 1 ml acetate buffer (pH 4.4 ± 0.05).

Matrix erosion test

After the swelling study, the matrix erosion test involved drying the swollen bioadhesive tablets (by acetate buffer of pH 4.6) at 60°C for 24 hr in an oven (W) and further keeping in desiccator for 48 hr and reweighed (W_0). Matrix erosion was calculated using following formula:

$$\text{Matrix erosion} = \frac{W - W_0}{W_0} \times 100$$

Bioadhesion strength

Bioadhesive strength of the vaginal tablets was measured on a Modified Physical Balance. The method involved sheep vaginal membrane as the model mucosal membrane. The fresh sheep vaginal mucosa was cut into pieces and washed with acetate buffer pH 4.6. A small piece of the mucosa was tied to the glass slide which was moistened with acetate buffer pH 4.6. The tablet was stuck to the lower side of another glass slide with glue. Both the pans were balanced by adding an appropriate weight. The glass slide with mucosa was placed with appropriate support so that the tablet touches the mucosa. Previously, the weighed beaker was placed on the pan and powder (equivalent to the weight) was added slowly to it until the tablet detach from the mucosal surface. The weight (in g) required to detach the tablet from the mucosal surface provides the bioadhesive strength. The experiment was performed in a triplicate manner and the average value was calculated. Bioadhesion strength was measured as the force of adhesion in Newton by using the formula:

$$\text{Force of adhesion} = \frac{\text{Mucoadhesive strength}}{100} \times 9.81$$

Bioadhesion time

The *ex vivo* mucoadhesion time was examined after application of the vaginal tablet on a freshly cut sheep vaginal mucosa. The fresh sheep vaginal mucosa was primarily tied on the glass slide. The mucoadhesive core side of each tablet was wetted with 1-2 drop of acetate buffer pH 4.6 and pasted to the sheep vaginal mucosa by applying a light force with a fingertip for 30 seconds. The glass slide was then put in the beaker which was filled with 200 mL of acetate buffer pH 4.6 and kept at $37 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. After 2 minutes, stirring was applied slowly to simulate the vaginal cavity environment and the tablet adhesion was monitored for 12 hr. The time taken by the tablet to detach from the sheep vaginal mucosa was recorded as the mucoadhesion time.

In vitro dissolution study

The *in vitro* drug release rate of acyclovir from the bioadhesive tablet was determined using USP 33 dissolution testing apparatus II (Paddle type). The dissolution test was performed using 900 mL pH 4.6 acetate buffer, without enzyme, at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ at a speed of 50 rpm for the duration of 12 hr. Aliquot sample of 5mL was withdrawn at predetermined time intervals using calibrated pipette from the dissolution media. An equivalent amount of fresh dissolution medium, maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ was added after withdrawing each sample to maintain the sink conditions. The drug content was determined using UV-visible spectrophotometer by measuring the absorbance of the solutions at 255 nm. The excipients employed in the formulation do not interfere with the assay. The release study was conducted in triplicate [24].

Release kinetics studies

For determining the drug release mechanism(s) from the bioadhesive tablet batches, the data acquired from the *in vitro* drug release studies were plotted in various kinetic models of Zero-order, First order, Higuchi, Hixson-Crowell, and Korsmeyer-Peppas models were used. Based on the goodness-of fit test, the most appropriate model was chosen. The correlation coefficient (r^2) and release exponent (n) were expressed for each model in correlation to the drug kinetics [25].

Accelerated stability studies

The F9 batch of the vaginal tablets was studied under the accelerated conditions of temperature ($40^\circ\text{C}\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) and moisture ($75\%\pm 5\%$ RH). The protocol involved weighing the tablet, wrapping in the aluminum foil, and packing it inside a black PVC bottle for the duration of 90 days. After the termination of the specified period, the tablet was withdrawn and evaluated in terms of physical appearance, mucoadhesive time, hardness, mucoadhesive force, drug content, % swelling, thickness, % matrix erosion, and *in vitro* drug release [26].

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The fabricated tablets were of diameter 10 mm. The physical characteristics of the tablet were found to be acceptable. The tablets were free from any defects like capping, picking, and chipping.

The drug-polymer interaction study highlighted no as such interaction of HPMC K15 or Carbopol 934P with acyclovir. The pure drug demonstrated characteristic peaks at 3522.13 (-OH stretching), 3441.12 (-NH₂ stretching), 1691.63 (-C=O stretching), 1631.83 (-C=N stretching), 1219.05 (C-O), and 1182.40 (C-N). In the physical mixture, same characteristic peaks were seen, which demonstrated that there was no drug polymer interaction and are compatible with each other (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. Drug-polymer interaction studies. (A) Acyclovir; (B) HPMC K15; (C) Carbopol 934P; and (D) Physical mixture.

The micromeritic characteristic of pure drug, carbapol 934P, and HPMC K15 were studied according to the standard procedure. The bulk and tapped densities were found to be less than 1.2 g/cm^3 , which indicated excellent packing of the drug particles. The Hausner's ratios and Carr's indexes were found to be in range, 1.19-1.57 and 16.32-36.40%, representing brilliant packing ability with acceptable flow properties. **Table 2** presents the micromeritic characteristics of the drug and polymers.

Table 2. Micromeritic parameters of drug and polymers.

Parameters	Acyclovir [#]	Carbopol 934P [#]	HPMC K15 [#]
Bulk density (g/cm^3)	0.412± 0.033	0.217± 0.021	0.304±0.038
Tapped density (g/cm^3)	0.493± 0.031	0.312± 0.018	0.478± 0.029
Carr's Index	16.32± 0.014	30.60±0.019	36.40±0.015
Hausner's ratio	1.19±0.017	1.43±0.013	1.57±0.011
Angle of repose	20±0.4	18±0.6	17±0.3

(n = 6), The total samples evaluated were 6.

All the formulations were assessed for their desired characteristic attributes as per standard procedures for evaluation. The average weight of tablets from all the formulation were found be in the range of 355-364 mg, which indicates that the all batches have the average standard weight as per the official standards. The drug content in all the batches of the formulation was in the range of 98.91-101.32%, reflecting uniform drug content practically. The thickness of the tablet was in the range of 3.21–3.25 mm. The surface pH of the tablet formulation batches was found to be in between 4.41-4.65 which indicated that the formulations were quite compatible for bioadhesion and will not irritate the mucosal surface. All the batches have good hardness and friability as per standards. The hardness of the fabricated tablets was found to be in range 5-6 kg/cm² and the friability of the batches was less than 1%. The parameters have stated that the prepared batches had the required strength to withstand wear and tear. The evaluation parameters of the prepared batches are illustrated in Table 3.

Table 3. Evaluation parameters of bioadhesive tablets.

Formulation	Thickness [#] (mm)	Hardness [#] (Kg/cm ²)	Friability [#] (%)	Average [#] weight (mg)	Drug content [#] (%)	Surface pH [#]
F1	3.25±0.01	5.4±0.2	0.53± 0.06	364±0.5	100.15±0.21	4.57±0.02
F2	3.22±0.04	5.1±0.3	0.54 ±0.03	361±0.5	99.24±0.37	4.61±0.04
F3	3.22±0.02	5.5±0.2	0.54 ±0.08	352±0.5	100.57±0.56	4.59±0.02
F4	3.25±0.01	5.2±0.3	0.56 ±0.02	362±0.5	99.83±0.33	4.64±0.01
F5	3.21±0.01	5.6±0.3	0.56±0.05	366±0.5	99.81±0.26	4.52±0.04
F6	3.26±0.03	5.3±0.2	0.53±0.06	359±0.5	99.66±0.44	4.41±0.02
F7	3.21±0.05	5.9±0.2	0.59 ±0.05	371±0.5	101.32±0.27	4.45±0.03
F8	3.25±0.01	5.7±0.1	0.58 ±0.02	358±0.5	100.05±0.62	4.57±0.01
F9	3.23±0.04	5.1±0.2	0.55 ±0.06	355±0.5	98.41±0.24	4.65±0.01

(n = 6), The total samples evaluated were 6.

The time for the tablet to detach from sheep vaginal mucosa was recorded as the mucoadhesion time. The formulation F7, containing the highest concentration of Carbopol 934P and HPMC K15 displayed highest mucoadhesion time (12.7 hr) and mucoadhesion force (0.22 N) as compared to other formulation (Figure 2a). However, the other prepared batches also expressed optimized mucoadhesion time and force (Figure 2b). The bioadhesive time, as well as the bioadhesive force, enhanced significantly as the concentration of carbopol 934P was increased. Many hydrophilic polymers adhere to mucosal surfaces as they attract water from the mucus gel layer adhering to the epithelial surface and more force required to detach the tablet from mucus membrane. The results of mucoadhesion time and force of the fabricated batches are depicted in Table 4.

Table 4. Microadhesion time and mucoadhesion force of the prepared batches.

Formulation	Mucoadhesion time (in hr)	Mucoadhesive force (in N)
F1	12.4±0.03	0.16±0.04
F2	12.1±0.23	0.15±0.02
F3	11.2±0.01	0.14±0.1
F4	12.3±0.02	0.17±0.01
F5	12.6±0.01	0.20±0.23
F6	12.3±0.01	0.16±0.12
F7	12.7±0.1	0.22±0.2
F8	12.3±0.2	0.14±0.01
F9	12.3±0.3	0.16±0.02

(n = 6), The total samples evaluated were 6.

All the tablet matrices were observed to be stable throughout the period of swelling and no tablet disintegration occurred. The swelling index of all formulations was found to be more or less superimposable due to the low invariance amongst their chosen polymer compositions. The swelling index profiles of all formulation, prepared as per the experimental design, are exemplified in Figure 2c.

Figure 2. Plots depicting attributes of the prepared batches: (A) Mucoadhesive Time (in hr); (B) Mucoadhesive Force (in N); (C) % Swelling Index; and (D) % Matrix Erosion.

The two used polymers; namely Carbopol 934P and HPMC K15 showed an enhancement in the values of the swelling index as the concentration gets increased. Formulation F7 expressed the higher swelling index owing to the higher concentration of HPMC K15 and carbapol 934P. The swelling index of the formulation batches were in the order: F2 < F1 < F5 < F4 < F8 < F9 < F3, which indicates that swelling is proportional to the ratio of polymer(s) used. The swelling behavior of the Carbopol 934P is attributed to the uncharged COOH group which become hydrated by forming hydrogen bonds with the imbibing water and therefore, extending the polymer chain. On the other hand, HPMC K15 is a hydrophilic polymer that swells to a significant extent upon contact with water. A high HPMC content results in a greater gel formation and forms a gelatinous barrier which retards drug release via diffusion through the gel and erosion of gel barrier (Figure 2d). On comparing the swelling indices of all formulations, it was observed that HPMC K15 swelled more than Carbopol 934P. Table 5 present the swelling index and erosion index of the prepared formulations.

Table 5. Swelling and matrix erosion study of the bioadhesive tablet batches.

Formulation	% Swelling Index (hr)						Matrix Erosion (%)
	2	4	6	8	10	12	
F1	17±0.1	38±0.23	57±0.3	82±0.03	96±0.04	109±0.02	31±0.02
F2	19±0.01	40±0.01	60±0.21	85±0.01	98±0.01	112±0.03	28±0.03
F3	20±0.02	45±0.2	65±0.21	74±0.11	90±0.01	103±0.3	40±0.01
F4	21±0.12	40±0.02	60±0.02	80±0.03	100±0.1	110±0.04	30±0.01
F5	16±0.32	37±0.02	55±0.03	80±0.1	95±0.03	107±0.03	32±0.02
F6	18±0.11	36±0.07	54±0.1	74±0.04	90±0.02	106±0.01	26±0.04
F7	20±0.2	45±0.01	75±0.2	100±0.01	107±0.1	120±0.04	27±0.01
F8	18±0.3	36±0.01	54±0.04	74±0.01	90±0.7	106±0.07	26±0.08
F9	17±0.11	40±0.04	59±0.04	77±0.03	90±0.1	104±0.1	26±0.08

(n = 6), The total samples evaluated were 6.

All the examined tablets belonging to the prepared formulations represented a sustain release pattern of drug release up to 12 hr. The results showed that as the concentration of the polymer present within the formulation increased, the amount of drug released was retarded. The formulation F3, which contain the least amount of Carbopol 934P and HPMC K15M exhibited maximum drug release, but not up to 12 hr (Figure 3). The overall rate of drug release at 12 hr tend to decrease with an increase in the amount of polymer in the formulations such as F7 < F2 < F1 < F5 < F4 < F8 < F9 < F3.

Figure 3. *In vitro* drug release profiles of bioadhesive vaginal tablet formulations. (A) Formulation F1-F3; (B) Formulation F4-F6; and (C) Formulation F7-F9.

In formulation F9, maximum drug release of 96% drug up to 12 hr at 15:25 optimum ratio of Carbapol 934P and HPMC K15. Carbapol 934P is a cross-linked polymer which when comes in contact with water, swells and hold water inside its microgel network. In the case of carbopol 934P, the carboxyl groups highly dissociate repulsion between the negatively charged carboxylic groups causing uncoiling and expansion of molecules and thus result in gel formation. This particular property may partially be responsible for the retarded drug release from acyclovir tablets. In the case of HPMC K15, which is also a hydrophilic swellable polymer, a similar retardant drug release pattern was observed. A high HPMC K15M content result in a greater amount of gel being formed which increased the diffusion path length of the drug. Hence, the drug release is controlled via diffusion through the gel and erosion of the gel barrier. The viscous nature also affects the diffusion coefficient of the drug, therefore, as a result, the drug release was found to be decreased as the amount of HPMC K15 gets increased. Table 6 explains the *in vitro* drug release profile of the formulation.

Table 6. *In vitro* drug release profile of bioadhesive vaginal tablet formulations.

	<i>In vitro</i> drug release (%)											
	1 hr	2 hr	3 hr	4 hr	5 hr	6 hr	7 hr	8 hr	9 hr	10 hr	11 hr	12 hr
F1	8.12 ±0.47	16.17 ±0.15	26 ±0.17	40.92 ±0.27	52.98 ±0.13	61.33 ±0.20	70.46 ±0.58	75.21 ±0.27	80.41 ±0.14	85.75 ±0.54	86.68 ±0.57	88.47 ±0.83
F2	8.27 ±0.51	17.62 ±0.68	29.38 ±0.23	44.77 ±0.76	56.14 ±0.38	65.49 ±0.56	74.32 ±0.18	80.17 ±0.45	85.79 ±0.99	89.35 ±0.72	90.76 ±0.66	92.74 ±0.31
F3	12.77 ±0.61	24.95 ±0.84	37.33 ±0.76	51.16 ±0.85	65.18 ±0.37	88.46 ±0.25	98.21 ±0.59	101.37 ±0.79	104.12 ±0.67	-	-	-
F4	7.46 ±0.21	17.83 ±0.95	29.61 ±0.17	43.37 ±0.60	56.73 ±0.71	66.53 ±0.25	75.62 ±0.58	80.34 ±0.19	84.46 ±0.97	88.27 ±0.16	90.45 ±0.40	92.93 ±0.66
F5	5.63 ±0.95	12.65 ±0.66	24.19 ±0.47	36.14 ±0.29	50.33 ±0.18	61.68 ±0.92	71.41 ±0.28	75.14 ±0.51	81.62 ±0.93	86.43 ±0.70	88.58 ±0.13	90.85 ±0.88
F6	7.72 ±0.48	18.49 ±0.87	30.44 ±0.62	46.69 ±0.34	55.71 ±0.75	67.63 ±0.42	74.81 ±0.36	77.29 ±0.77	82.76 ±0.64	88.54 ±0.37	91.17 ±0.46	92.29 ±0.25
F7	7.37 ±0.14	14.47 ±0.15	25.11 ±0.27	37.75 ±0.92	52.93 ±0.62	61.24 ±0.80	70.43 ±0.23	74.32 ±0.72	80.3 ±0.81	85.4 ±0.55	87.78 ±0.12	89.11 ±0.49
F8	9.56 ±0.68	18.69 ±0.23	30.84 ±0.86	42.28 ±0.50	55.39 ±0.13	64.57 ±0.36	72.43 ±0.15	76.62 ±0.91	82.99 ±0.48	88.52 ±0.30	92.27 ±0.54	93.24 ±0.31
F9	12.67 ±0.63	24.91 ±0.17	35.56 ±0.98	52.88 ±0.35	61.25 ±0.57	70.97 ±0.26	75.42 ±0.76	80.67 ±0.73	86.13 ±0.45	90.48 ±0.92	94.31 ±0.24	96.64 ±0.32

(n = 6), The total samples evaluated were 6.

The comparison of the mechanism of drug release from swellable matrices could be determined by several physicochemical phenomena. Among them, polymer water uptake, gel layer formation, and polymeric chain relaxation are primarily involved in the modulation of drug release. On application of different release models, the correlation coefficient (r^2) and release exponent (n) of the formulations were found to be exhibiting non-Fickian release kinetics, which is indicative of drug release mechanisms involving diffusion. The formulation F9, demonstrating the highest drug release was observed to follow the Korsmeyer-Peppas model, as indicated by the release exponent (n) of 0.5168 (Table 7). A constant drug release rate with time has been observed, from a constant geometry till the polymer chains rearrange to an equilibrium state. The drug transport mechanism(s) followed non-Fickian diffusion which coincides with swelling erosion mechanism. The drug release process was governed by two processes; diffusion as well as erosion (often represented as anomalous diffusion).

Table 7. Kinetics of drug release from tablet formulations.

Formulation code	Zero order r^2	First order r^2	Higuchi r^2	Hixson-Crowell r^2	Koremayer-Peppas n
F1	0.8163	0.9142	0.9729	0.9319	0.6608
F5	0.8689	0.9401	0.8946	0.8879	0.5777
F9	0.9008	0.9887	0.9426	0.8521	0.5168

The accelerated stability study ($40^\circ\text{C}\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $75\%\pm 5\%$ RH for 90 days) of the bioadhesive tablets displayed no noticeable alterations in terms of physical appearance, mucoadhesive time, hardness, mucoadhesive force, drug content, % swelling, thickness, % matrix erosion, and *in vitro* drug release of batch F9 formulation. No remarkable dissimilarity was observed in terms of thickness, % swelling, hardness, and % matrix erosion. Although, a small change in drug content (0.17 %) was identified. In summary, it might be concluded that the prepared bioadhesive vaginal matrix tablet was stable under accelerated conditions and will remain stable under storage conditions. Table 8 portrays the differences before and after stability study.

Table 8. Alterations in tablet formulation after accelerated stability study.

Parameters	0 days	90 days
Physical appearance	White smooth texture	No changes observed
Thickness (in mm)	3.23 ± 0.01	3.22 ± 0.01
Hardness (in Kg/cm^2)	5.1 ± 0.2	4.9 ± 0.3
Mucoadhesive time (in hr)	12.3 ± 0.19	12.1 ± 0.16
Mucoadhesive force (in N)	0.16 ± 0.26	0.15 ± 0.21
Drug content (%)	98.41 ± 0.44	98.24 ± 0.71
Cumulative drug release % (at 12 hr)	96.66 ± 0.08	95.97 ± 0.09

(n = 6), The total samples evaluated were 6.

CONCLUSION

The current study indicated that the hydrophilic matrix tablet of acyclovir, formulated employing only hypromellose and carbomer can successfully be employed as twice daily, very economic bioadhesive vaginal controlled release dosage form. The formulation was found to be suitable with respect to bioadhesive and sustained release characteristic. For treating local as well systemic infections, the formulation will successfully deliver the dose for the frequency of 2 times per day as compared to the conventional tablet dosage form which requires dosing of 4 to 5 times per day. The *in vitro* drug release study revealed that the formulation F9 delivered 96% of the drug in 12 hr duration. The results indicated a steady state sustained release pattern throughout 12 hr of the study which will improve the patient convenience due to less frequency of drug administration. The polymeric materials were found to be quite cheap, easily available, have high safety levels, and have regulatory approval. The research has the perspectives in commercialization of control release bioadhesive vaginal tablets since the optimized formulation delivers the desired pharmacotherapeutic regimen.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There is no conflict of interest for the publication of this article.

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